

THE ROLE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ATHEROSCLEROTIC STENOTIC LESIONS OF THE CAROTID ARTERIES

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Summary. In order to improve the results of diagnosis and surgical treatment of patients with atherosclerotic lesions of carotid arteries we investigated endothelial dysfunction in patients with atherosclerotic stenosis. A methods for diagnosis of endothelial dysfunction was assessment of changes in brachial artery diameter before and after a short limb ischemia and plasma homocysteine levels. Object of the study: 72 patients, 38 of which were undergone standard carotid endarterectomy, eversion carotid endarterectomy was performed in other 34 persons. Results and discussion. 57(79,2 %) patients had impaired vasodilation, 68 (94.4 %) persons had increased homocysteine concentration. After classical carotid endarterectomy homocysteine concentration was significantly increased from $15,90 \pm 4,26$ to $118,4 \pm 4,2$ $\mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p < 0.05$), after eversion carotid endarterectomy — from $13,30 \pm 3,27$ to $14,2 \pm 5,6$ $\mu\text{mol/l}$. According to the results of both tests more intensive endothelial dysfunction was observed in patients with diffuse atherosclerotic lesions. In the postoperative period, the growth of the homocysteine concentration was observed in the group after classical carotid endarterectomy in comparison with eversion carotid endarterectomy

Keywords: atherosclerotic stenosis, endothelial dysfunction, carotid endarterectomy, homocysteine, endothelium-dependent vasodilation

Cerebrovascular diseases, and ischemic stroke in particular, remain one of the most pressing problems of modern neurology. Despite the measures taken, stroke already ranks second among the causes of death in developed countries, being between cardiac and oncological pathology. One in ten people in the world dies from a stroke, and only one in three stroke patients returns to their previous work. According to some authors, a further increase in mortality from stroke is predicted in the future [1]. In 80% of cases, the lesion is ischemic in nature and in most patients develops due to narrowing of the vessels supplying blood to the brain [4]. Most often, stenosis is caused by an atherosclerotic plaque in the internal carotid artery, which leads to a decrease in cerebral blood flow and creates conditions for the development of ischemic changes in the brain

tissue. In order to prevent the development of ischemic cerebral circulation disorders, carotid endarterectomy is performed from the affected segment of the carotid artery. Despite the continuing interest in the problem of choosing a method of surgical revascularization of the carotid arteries, risk factors have not yet been systematized, the correction of which will reduce the number of complications, and a modern prognostic model has not been developed regarding the outcomes of surgical treatment of carotid stenoses. The study of endothelial function in patients with cerebrovascular insufficiency of the brain, as the main pathogenetic link of arterial hypertension and atherosclerosis, is especially relevant. [5, 6]. The vascular endothelium is a thin semi-permeable membrane lining the heart and blood vessels from the inside, which continuously produces a huge amount of the most important biologically active substances and controls many important functions [6-10]. It plays a very important role in angiogenesis due to the fact that it has vasomotor, antiplatelet, anticoagulant, thrombolytic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antiproliferative activity [2, 3]. The barrier role of the vascular endothelium determines its main role in the human body: maintaining homeostasis by regulating the equilibrium state of opposite processes:

- a) vascular tone (vasodilation/vasoconstriction);
- b) anatomical structure of blood vessels (synthesis/inhibition of proliferation factors);
- c) hemostasis (synthesis and inhibition of fibrinolysis and platelet aggregation factors);
- d) local inflammation (production of pro- and anti-inflammatory factors).

The metabolic activity of the endothelium manifests itself in the main vessels, exerting an additional effect on the entire circulatory regulation system. Vascular hypertension, increased peripheral resistance and compensatory arterial hypertension (AH) with all possible complications arise due to failures of vasodilation mechanisms, in particular, insufficiency of endothelium-dependent dilation or endothelial dysfunction. Vasoconstriction, spasmation of the muscular components of the vascular wall proceeds much faster and more energetically than their relaxation. Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is manifested by a violation of the neurohumoral regulation of vascular tone, their remodeling and activation of thrombogenesis and inflammation in the vascular wall. In particular, it can cause vasospasm, increased thrombosis and increased adhesion of leukocytes to the endothelium, which is accompanied by a violation of regional blood circulation and microcirculation. ED has been identified in

metabolic syndrome and dyslipidemia and may be associated with obesity, hyperhomocysteinemia, sedentary lifestyle and smoking in [13]. After nicotine consumption, the number of circulating endothelial cells in the peripheral blood increases, which is a sign of increased desquamation of the endothelium. According to the hypothesis of atherogenesis, called "response to injury", it is the damage to endotheliocytes and the development of endothelial dysfunction that become the first stage of atherosclerosis.

According to the results of a number of clinical studies, the D.S. Celermajer ESRD test was recognized as an adequate diagnostic test for diagnosing ED [12]. Despite the intensive study of ED, there is only limited data on the relationship between EDV and markers of atherosclerotic lesion of peripheral vessels. A decrease in the dilation response of the brachial artery in patients with peripheral vascular atherosclerosis in several clinical prospective studies was associated with a worse prognosis.

The endothelium has vasomotor, antiplatelet, anticoagulant, thrombolytic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antiproliferative activity, it plays an extremely important role in the development of atherosclerotic changes in the vascular wall, vascular remodeling, angiogenesis [1, 4, 15]. Endothelial function can be defined as a balance of oppositely acting principles - relaxing and constrictor factors, anticoagulant and procoagulant factors, growth factors and their inhibitors. In turn, ED is a violation of this dynamic equilibrium [6, 7]. Most biologically active substances secreted by endothelial cells, as well as those involved in the process of interaction with the endothelium, can be indicators of its function. ED, as the earliest phase of vascular wall damage, can act as one of the sensitive markers of cardiovascular diseases [2].

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